

Analysis and implementation of different shifting solutions for a 2-speed AMT gearbox.

Chitra Bahadur NAHARKEE¹, Kevin TREVEY¹, Hellen DA SILVA¹

1: IFP School, Powertrain Engineering Program, Rueil-Malmaison, 92501, FR

2: ARRIVAL, Beaumont House, Kensington Village, London, W14 8TS, GB

Supervisors: Nicolangelo Piscitelli², Alexandre Charr²

Abstract: As part of the IFP School, PWT Engineering curriculum, a research project in collaboration with a company named ARRIVAL was accomplished. The purpose of this project was to analyze and implement different gear shifting solutions for a 2-speed Automated Manual Transmission (AMT) equipped electric commercial delivery van to optimize shifting quality, driving comfort, performance, efficiency, and reliability. This paper investigates the design of a new transmission system without a friction synchronizer. Active speed sensing technology for the output shaft, along with the potential of speed matching using electric motors and implementation of torsional springs to dampen the possible shock that can be produced due to the speed, or the position error, eliminating the need for the friction synchronizer. An electrically controlled camshaft-type rotational actuator with a DC shift motor is implemented to the transmission system. Cascade controller is proposed to control the position of the actuator and the input voltage of the DC motor. A PWM driver is used to control the rotational speed and the direction of the DC motor by varying the duty cycle. A 1D Simscape-Simulink based gearbox and vehicle model were built up to simulate the behavior of the proposed shifting solutions. Running the Simulink model on different duty-cycles and analyzing different sets of actuators and clutches to optimize gearbox's performance and efficiency indicated that 1 actuator with 1 dog clutch configuration provides a significant improvement in shifting quality, vehicle's performance, and efficiency.

Keywords: Electric Commercial Delivery Van, 2-speed AMT gearbox, Dog clutch, camshaft type rotational shift actuator, Gear Shifting Strategy.

1. Introduction

1.1 Target

Because of zero fuel consumption and emission, battery electric vehicle (BEV) is thought to be the ideal solution for the energy crisis and global warming. Arrival's aim is to create a cost-effective 2-speed AMT-equipped commercial electric vehicle with a high level of efficiency, autonomy, and performance. One of the most important and delicate components to achieve the Arrival's target is gearbox and gear shifting control system that must guarantee the safe and smooth gear shifts to ensure the

integrity of the mechanical parts and a high level of drivability. In general, BEV's are integrated with a single-speed transmission that has difficulties meeting the frequent starts & stops and high torque transmission requirements when they have a large load.

Target is to develop a physical model of a 2-speed AMT gearbox and to study different gear shifting solutions and implement its control model.

The powertrain environment should comply with the following rules:

- E-motor data is given with efficiency maps and maximum power/torque information.
- Inverter, gearbox, and half shaft efficiency should be considered as constant values.
- Reduction ratios must be adjusted within the limits from **2:1** to **10:1**.

1.2 Requirements and project organization

The baseline vehicle specifications for the simulation process are shown below.

Table 1: Baseline Vehicle Specifications

Characteristics	Value	Unit	Label
Wheel radius	0.343	m	
Rolling resistance coefficient	0.0067	-	
Aerodynamic drag coefficient	0.348	-	
Vehicle frontal area	5.207	m ²	
Grip coefficient	0.8	-	
Axle loading factor	0.45	-	
Fully laden vehicle mass	4000	kg	
Unladen vehicle mass	2100	Kg	
Gravitational Acceleration	9.81	m/s ²	
Air density	1.225	kg/m ³	

Motor and inverter characteristics were provided and kept the same for all scenarios. The inverter, gearbox and half-shafts efficiencies are kept 98%, 97%, and 98% simultaneously. The e-motor efficiency map is shown below.

Figure 1: e-motor efficiency map

Since the targeted vehicle is an electric delivery van, the lower part (up to 600 [sec]) of the WLTC class 3 driving cycle with the maximum vehicle speed of 56.5 [km/h] is assumed to be sufficient to simulate the targeted vehicle behavior. The error of the actual vehicle speed and the drive cycle speed must not be higher than 3% on average, with no more than 10% deviation at maximum.

Figure 2: WLTC class 3 driving cycle

The starting weight and ending weight of the vehicle is considered 70% and 30% of the fully laden mass respectively, assuming the vehicle weight will linearly decrease from the beginning till the end of the cycle. Since the paper focuses more on shifting solutions rather than the vehicle behavior, gradeability is not considered in the model.

The first step for the project organization was to study and analyze the provided materials, Arrival's requirements regarding the different shifting solutions such as shifting with/without synchronizers, type and number of actuators and clutches, shifting algorithms, etc. along with the control model, then to set up the roadmap to achieve the project target.

Literature review and analysis were essential to effectively proceed with the project regarding the

gear shifting with or without synchronizer, gear shifting mechanism & strategies in either case.

Thanks to the literature, Arrival's support combined with the knowledge from the IFP school PWT Program, we have succeeded to come up with a dog clutch and active speed sensing technology based shifting solution without the need of friction synchronizer, electrically controlled camshaft-type rotational actuator to engage/disengage the clutch and 1D MATLAB® Simulink® based gearbox physical model, control model, and a vehicle model to simulate the behaviors and performance impact of our solutions.

The gearbox 1D longitudinal physical model allowed us to study several parameters impacting the gearbox performance such as: the shifting strategy, actuator and clutch solutions, number of actuator and clutch configuration, etc. Finally, the best performing, and energy-saving solution would be targeted, while considering other aspects such as the cost penalty for each shifting solution, compactness, reliability, durability, etc.

1.3 Project roadmap

The overall project planning can be divided into 6 major topics that are summarized below and apportioned on the roadmap in Figure 3. All the tasks accomplished during the project duration of 16 weeks were continuously divided among 3 students of the project.

- ◆ Objectives and project organization
- ◆ Gear shifting technologies analysis
- ◆ Physical model development
- ◆ Control model development
- ◆ Matlab environment development
- ◆ Report and presentation preparation

Figure 3: Project roadmap

The first project kick-off meeting with Arrival's supervisors took place on week 11. Then, seven efficient meetings were organized in total during the project, in which, progressive topics were discussed together to step up the next target each time. Thanks to the proper guidance and validation from Arrival's supervisors' team that we were able to complete the project in time. On W27, the results of the project were presented in front of juries

composed by the teachers from IFP school, instructors from other companies/institutions and Arrival's supervisors.

2. Literatures Review

Different gear shifting solutions were analyzed, implemented, and simulated during the project, based on the relevant literature to decide the most suitable and efficient solution for the Arrival's commercial electric delivery van. The selected appropriate shifting solutions with 1 actuator and 1 dog clutch, active speed sensing technology integrated transmission system without friction synchronizers is expected to fulfill Arrival's objectives of performance, efficiency, comfort, smoothness, cost, packaging at the same time.

2.1 Dog Clutches and their engagement

Friction clutches are commonly used in automatic transmissions to ensure smooth clutch engagement and disengagement and good shift quality. However, efficiency losses occur during the energized mode because of the slip due to the viscous drag between the friction plates. Further, multi-plate friction clutches consume considerable space and thus pose challenges when designing a compact transmission. Driven by the demand for a better electrical energy economy, the concept to replace friction clutches with dog clutches is worthwhile to be investigated. Compared to friction clutch, the dog clutch is more compact and provides lower drag losses. Chengu et al [3] focused on developing component level modeling of dog clutch to improve the drivability by implementing Spring-Damper systems to control the vibro-impacts oscillation to ensure the safe transmission

In general, an additional dog teeth position sensor is required to make sure that the grounded dog and engaging dog are not in the same phase that refrains from the driving and driven dog collision. [4] proposed 2 different estimation algorithms, direct method & Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) to estimate the best moment for the dog engagement that uses the actuator feedback signal to determine the angular position of the dog sleeves, avoiding the need of additional position sensors, reducing the cost, complexity, noise, and wear in the transmission. The first estimation method estimates the suitable dog engagement moment based on the phase differences between driven and driving dog while the other method 'PSO' updates the velocity and position at each iteration to determine the ideal moment for the engagement.

2.2 Transmission system without friction synchronizers

Synchronizers are often used in manual and automated manual transmission systems to allow smooth gear shifting. Their primary purpose is to match the speeds between an input shaft and an

output shaft, but they also prevent the gears on the shafts from experiencing high levels of shock, noise, and backlash and help reduce gear wear. Most often dog clutches are coupled with the Synchronizers and utilize friction to engage the dog teeth to lock the gears for torque transmission. The dog clutch without a synchronizer has been applied in commercial and military vehicles however, information on dog clutch-based transmission systems without friction synchronizers are very limited.

Alowayed et al [1] developed an "Active Position Sensing" technology that can accurately track the angular position and velocity of the dog-attached gears at any moment using electromagnetic sensing that ascertains the RPM difference of the two gear systems, which then gives an idea to tune the motor speed controller to ensure the RPM difference within ± 30 RPM for the engagement, avoiding the need of friction synchronizers. The transmission design consists of a torsional compliance with multiple springs (Figure [7]) in between coupling device to prevent possible shock due to angular velocity difference between controlled input shaft attached to the electric motor and the uncontrolled output shaft attached to the transmission. The dog clutch design is centered to lower the excessive backlash that can lead to unwanted noise, consisting of 7 pairs of teeth in total, one tooth being longer than another for each pair as shown in figure [5]. Longer tooth is used for the engagement while the shorter one engages later to prevent the backlash.

2.3 shift actuators

Actuators achieve the physical movement or motion by converting one form of energy, often hydraulic, electric, magnetic into mechanical forces that allows establishing the link among multiple physical components. Shift actuators are very important components in the transmission system as they highly influence the shifting time, energy consumption and the driving comfort, etc.

The most common shift actuators in the transmission market today are hydraulic systems due to their high force density. However, such systems are inefficient in terms of energy consumption, due to the need for continuous increased pressure, even when no gear shift event is commanded.

Electromagnetic actuators are another common type of shifting actuators that convert electrical energy into mechanical energy to gain motion using an electromagnetic force induces in the coil of the actuator. An output shaft is moved by the electromagnetic force, induced by electric current and permanent magnets, to perform the gear change. [15] described the design of moving coil-type electromagnetic linear actuator that is one of the prevailing solutions due to its high force and low inertia. Advanced feedforward and feedback combined controller is developed to obtain faster response and good accuracy compared to the

setpoint. Lin et al. [7] presented an electromagnetic actuator with a linear and a rotary part. A linear electromagnetic actuator was studied in [9] and gives the complete picture of the actuation mechanism for the actuator and the control strategies required in the gearbox to implement it.

Drum/Camshaft type actuator is another common type of shifting actuator that functions by the mechanical forces as stated by Liu et al. in [9] and inferred that it's one of the most suitable solutions for a 2-speed AMT gearbox. [9] proposed a simplified prototype structure of an electrically controlled shift actuator that is compact, lighter, simple in layout & structure. The performance of the electrically controlled actuator is validated by the simulations.

2.3 Gear shift control strategy

The operating modes of AMTs are usually two: semi-automatic, with the driver requesting a sequential gear shift by means of a proper interface, or fully automatic. In both cases, after the gear shift request, the Transmission Control Unit (TCU) takes the control of the shifting strategy, by issuing suitable command signals to motor, the actuators, and the gearbox, according to current motor regime, driving conditions and driving mode [12]. In addition to the TCU, the other controllers including Vehicle Management System (VMS) and Motor Control Unit (MCU) are needed to accomplish the gear shift operation [11].

Once the TCU makes the shift decision based on the optimal shift schedule, gear-shift control process begins including 7 different phases: shift request phase, motor to free mode phase, gear release phase, synchronization phase, motor to free mode again phase, gear engagement phase, torque recovery phase [11] in a 2-speed synchronesh AMT gearbox integrated BEV. In [12], a finite state automaton for a synchronesh 2-speed AMT gearbox is presented.

2.4 Reduction ratios optimization

In general, maximum gradeability sets the highest value of gear ratio (i.e., 1st gear), and the maximum desirable speed sets the limit on the lowest gear ratio. The low value of gear ratio also contributes to the energy economy that is usually measured by the state of charge (SOC) of the battery. Therefore, a high step ratio (highest gear ratio/lowest gear ratio) can improve both dynamic and economic performances [8] but it invites another challenge with smooth gear shifting while changing the gear. Set of gear ratios with the lowest value of electrical energy consumption will be the optimal values for multi-speed transmission system.

3. Transmission system and shifting solutions

Dog clutches and active speed sensing technologies are used to perform the gear engagement, and their advantages are analyzed in this section. First, unlike traditional AMT, this solution doesn't require friction synchronizers. Second, a camshaft type rotational shifting actuator is introduced. Third, different gear shifting algorithms and shifting control strategies based on the motor torque demand are designed. Fourth, a 1D longitudinal gearbox & vehicle simulation model is created in matlab/Simulink environment to analyze the advantages of different solutions and to optimize the gearbox performance, considering the electrical energy consumption from the vehicle model. The major components and technologies of the 2-speed AMT are further discussed below.

Figure 4: 2-speed AMT without synchronizer

3.1 Dog clutches – Design and engagement

Driven by the demand of optimized gearbox performance and vehicle's energy consumption, the concept to replace friction clutches with dog clutches is worthwhile to be investigated due to the lower drag losses and compactness. This paper presents a simplified component level model of a dog clutch and its contact dynamics and the different stages of dog clutch engagement.

Dog clutches are usually made up of an engaging part that is directly mounted to the input shaft and a grounded part that is usually isolated with the gear system or the gear being drilled to open an engaging window to be used as a grounded side itself. As shown in Figure 5, assuming one side dog is completely grounded, the other engaging dog having two different teethes of different lengths (figure 9) with an initial rotating speed is actuated axially to engage the longer tooth a little earlier & followed quickly by the shorter tooth to prevent backlash, the normal contact force F_{normal} between engaging and grounded dogs can be represented by contact stiffness K_{normal} , contact damping C_{normal} , relative displacement x_{normal} and relative velocity \dot{x}_{normal} along the normal direction.

Figure 5: Dog-to-Dog vibro-impacts dynamics

$$F_{normal} = K_{normal}x_{normal} + C_{normal}\dot{x}_{normal} \quad (1)$$

Through kinematic analysis, x_{normal} , \dot{x}_{normal} can be calculated as a function of angular displacement (θ) of the engaging dog as in [3]. Further, vibro-impacts could occur due to the angular clearance that causes the relative motion in axial and rotational direction to impact the force on normal direction as shown in equation (2) where ε is the clearance that varies with the axial displacement.

$$F_{normal} = \begin{cases} K_{normal}(x_{normal} + \varepsilon) & \theta < -\varepsilon \\ 0 & -\varepsilon \leq \theta \leq \varepsilon \\ K_{normal}(x_{normal} - \varepsilon) & \theta > \varepsilon \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The normal force, together with the friction force can be decomposed into axial force and tangential force (Figure 5) as shown in equation (3) & (4), where μ is the friction coefficient. Tangential force provides bending moment on the supporting shaft in the same direction as friction ($-\mu$) and the axial force acts like a compression force on the normal plane, on which the friction force continuously opposes the movement ($+\mu$).

$$F_{axial} = \mu F_{normal} \quad (3)$$

$$F_{tangential} = -\mu F_{normal} \quad (4)$$

Then, the governing equations for the 2-DoF system (engaging dog) along the axial direction (equation (5)) and rotational or tangential direction (equation (6)) can be generated and the derived physics can be used to actuate the dog clutches. Where, M is the mass of the engaging dog, $F_e(t)$ is the axial actuation force that can be time-varying or time-invariant, J_g is the moment of inertia, T_g is the external or inertial torque associated with the engaging dog and R is the radius of the engaging dog.

$$M\ddot{x} = F_e(t) - F_{axial} \quad (5)$$

$$J_g\ddot{\theta}_g = T_g - F_{tangential}R \quad (6)$$

The engagement of the dog clutches needs multiple stages [3] depending on the initial angle,

angular displacement of the engaging dog. Engaging dog spin speed can be reversed or can slightly bounce back if the engaging side tooth collide with the ground side tooth while trying to move forward. Therefore, it is very important to implement torsional system such as spring or damper or both to restore the kinetic energy during collision to ensure the safe and reliable engagement.

Figure 6: Dog Clutch engagement

3.2 Active speed sensing technology

Active speed sensing technology for the output shaft is investigated to track the accurate rotational speed of the output shaft at any moment using electromagnetic sensing and makes it possible to ascertain the difference in speeds of two gear systems during a shift and control the motor speed to the correct speed for engagement within ± 30 RPM. This technology, in combination with motor control, can perform the same function as the friction synchronizer and thus eliminates the need for the friction synchronizer in the transmission system. However, by removing these friction synchronizer components, significant shocks could be introduced to the transmission system with speed or position errors during a shift that can lead to undesirable drivability, material fatigue and durability. Furthermore, the frequent acceleration and deceleration of the vehicle under normal operation can cause large gaps or backlash in the drivetrain. Another requirement is the ability to couple and decouple the gears seamlessly to minimize the risk of engagement and disengagement failure. This paper proposes a solution through a gear system that utilizes a face mesh design, torsional springs, and alternating teeth height to prevent the above-mentioned shock and backlash phenomenon that is discussed below.

3.2.1 Shock Prevention

It is expected that active speed sensing technology would advance enough to not require shock prevention methods. However, without friction synchronizers, which matches the speeds exactly, the rotational inertia must be dealt with to reduce the slamming of engaging elements. Due to the accuracy of the speed control of the electric motor, there may exist a small difference in angular velocity between the controlled input shaft attached to the electric motor and the uncontrolled output shaft attached to the car that causes to produce the slamming force. It can be characterized by the peak acceleration during engagement.

Figure 7: Sketch of the Torsional Compliance [1]

Lowering the torsional stiffness of the system will limit the peak acceleration of the engagement event by absorbing the kinetic energy and releasing it over a larger timescale. This can be achieved by adding compliant elements such as springs or rubber components at radial position between the engaging dog clutches as shown in Figure 8. The torsional springs compress in the rotational direction to deal with the rotational inertia and prevents the shock.

Figure 8: Exploded view of transmission system [1]

3.2.2 Backlash Prevention

Backlash is a result of undercut angle of the dogteeth, which are required to hold the gears in the engaged position, and gaps such that the teeth can properly engage. However, too much backlash can lead to unwanted noise and driving behavior.

To reduce backlash, we propose a new design that incorporates teeth of two different lengths. The longer tooth (tooth ① in figure 9) enters the cavity first, followed quickly by the smaller bottom tooth (tooth ②), helping to increase the engagement window (③ in figure 9) and reduce backlash. This design would lower the number of engagement windows available but would simultaneously make each window larger, preventing from backlash.

Figure 9: Double tooth length design [1]

3.3 Camshaft-type rotational actuators

The design and optimization of shift actuators have always been the key point in full electric AMT vehicles. The performance of the shift actuator influences the shift quality significantly. Moreover, the shift quality makes an impact on the shift time and the riding comfort. Among various types of AMT shift actuators, the electrically controlled shift actuator is simpler, quicker, and easier to control. The two-speed AMT for electric vehicles and the shift actuator in this study have the following features: compact size leads to a lighter gearbox, easy access to layout design, and better assembling capacity. A simple control strategy makes the electric system more robust.

Figure 10: 3D Model of a shift actuator [9]

The shift actuator mainly consists of the shift fork (machined with a round pin that can be mounted with the engaging side dogs), fork shaft, camshaft (machined with a groove), worm gear, and a shift motor (a small DC motor). The schematic diagram of the camshaft-type shift actuator is shown below in figure 11.

Figure 11: Schematic diagram of shift actuator [9]

During the shift process, the shift motor rotation is transformed into the axial motion of the shift fork through the worm gear and camshaft, so that the engaging side dog clutch mounted to the shift fork can move along the axial direction for the engagement and disengagement.

Figure 12: Camshaft rotation direction [9]

The shift fork is pushed by the groove in the camshaft, and the expanded view of the groove is shown in Figure 13. The shift fork position control is the key to ensure the shift quality to push or pull the dog clutches, and the position of the groove can be reflected by the camshaft rotation angle measured by an angular displacement sensor.

Figure 13: Expanded view of Groove in camshaft [9]

The groove is divided into five parts, including the rotation angle part of the first gear (part 1), the first gear slope (part 2), rotation angle part of neutral (part 3), the second gear slope (part 4), and the rotation angle part of the second gear (part 5).

When the shift fork pin is at a rotation angle part of the groove, the shift fork cannot move in the axial direction, although the camshaft is rotating, which guarantees the control accuracy of the engaging dog clutch movements in the shifting process.

3.4 Gear shifting strategy

Gear shifting strategy is defined to provide the state flow with logical conditions that determines when to upshift and when to downshift. The main target of it was to shift the gears to keep the e-Motor working at the most efficient zone during the entire driving cycle and to minimize the energy consumption as well as to limit the number of shifts to avoid continuous unwanted shifting. The following

criteria (Table 2) were introduced to the state flow to cope with the shifting strategy.

- **E-Motor Efficiency:** shifting is executed if it supposes an improvement on efficiency by at least 1%.
- **Available torque:** shifting is executed if new gear grants enough torque to follow the targeted vehicle speed, considering the maximum torque that the e-Motor can handle at each operating point.
- **Acceleration threshold:** Some unwanted shifts were taking place close to no acceleration demand. So, a threshold value of acceleration for which it is not worth to target a shift was calibrated. Since there is no regeneration mode considered in this model, the shifting when vehicle acceleration in negative is undesired.
- **Minimum time a gear must be engaged:** to avoid unwanted continuous shifts, a minimal time 5 [sec] to keep engaged in the same gear was defined, mainly to avoid repeated downshift followed by quick upshift back to the previous gear and vice versa.

Table 2: Gear Shifting Strategy

Execution order	Shifting type	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3	Condition 4	Condition 5	Condition 6
1	Downshift to $\nearrow \eta_{motor}$	η_{motor} gain > 1 %	η_{motor} down > η_{motor} Up	Torque enough	Last upshift occurred at least 5s before	Last downshift occurred at least 0.5s before	Acceleration > 0.15 m/s ²
2	Upshift to $\nearrow \eta_{motor}$	η_{motor} gain > 1	Torque enough	Last downshift occurred at least 5s before	Last upshift occurred at least 0.5s before	Acceleration > 0.15 m/s ²	
3	Downshift to \nearrow Torque	Torque not enough for current gear	Torque enough for targeted gear				
4	Upshift to \nearrow Torque	Torque not enough for current gear	Torque enough for targeted gear				

3.5 Shifting control

Since, the actuator is actuated by a shift electric motor, it is necessary to control the current passing to the motor to control the torque and rotation of motor. The equivalent circuit of the proposed dc shift motor when connected to a source voltage is shown in figure 14.

Figure 14: Equivalent electrical circuit

E_a , I_a , R , L , E_c represent source voltage, motor (armature) current, resistance, equivalent inductance, induced E.M.F by the motor.

The input voltage will be,

$$E_a = E_c + RI(t) + L \frac{dI(t)}{dt} \quad (7)$$

The output voltage from the motor will be,

$$E_c = k_e * N \quad (8)$$

Where, k_e is power generation constant, N is the shift motor RPM. Since the motor output torque is directly proportional to the motor input current, the motor torque can be calculated as

$$T(t) = k_t * I(t) \quad \rightarrow \quad I(t) = \frac{T(t)}{k_t} \quad (9)$$

Where, k_t is the torque constant, N is the shift motor RPM. By using equation (5) and (6), it is possible to control the position of the actuator shift fork by knowing the forces required to push/pull the dog clutch, while the equation (9) along with the PWM controller allows to control the speed and direction of rotation of the DC shift motor by varying the duty cycle.

$$\text{Duty Cycle(\%)} = \frac{T_{\text{ON}}}{T_{\text{ON}} + T_{\text{OFF}}} * 100\% \quad (10)$$

A cascade control method with feedback control as shown in Figure 15 is expected to be the optimum control solution for the proposed actuator system.

Figure 15: Actuator Controller

The cascade control system gets the information of the targeted gear from the shifting

strategy. The desired position of the actuator shift fork is calculated as

$$\text{Actuator Position} = \text{longer tooth height} + \text{Engaging \& grounded dog clearance when disengaged} \quad (11)$$

At first, the input shaft motor speed is necessary to be controlled to match the RPM difference of input and output shaft by using the active speed sensing technology. When the error is less than 30 RPM, the motor control system permits to make the shift. The actuator receives the information of targeted gear and the shift fork control by another small shift motor will then move towards positive or negative axial direction to engage the dog clutch to select the 1st or the 2nd gear.

4. Development of 1-D models

4.1 Longitudinal Model of the Delivery Van

Simulink model is created to simulate the influence of transmission model in the vehicle model. The parameters predefined in Table 2 along with the information of driving cycle, mass cycle, etc. are utilized to study their impact on vehicle performance. The main parts of the model are explained below.

Figure 16: Main structure of the vehicle model

1. **Driving cycle:** provides the speed-time profile of a real-world driving situations.
2. **Controller:** PID controller regulates the process variables.
3. **Longitudinal Dynamics:** includes all the longitudinal equations of the vehicle dynamics and driveline dynamics.
4. **E-motor efficiency Map:** provides the information of the motor efficiency for any speed/torque variations.
5. **State flow:** logic component that selects the most optimal operating point depending on the targets and thresholds (logic conditions) introduced to it.
6. **Gearbox:** allows to change the gear ratio depending on the torque and speed demand.

4.2 Gearbox physical model

The input shaft of a pure electric vehicle is always rotating at higher RPM. So, reducer system is necessary to lower the RPM as well as to increase the torque. Actuator pushes the dog clutch in axial direction either towards the 1st gear or the 2nd gear to engage the gear.

Figure 17: Gearbox model

The gearbox model receives the input torque from an e-motor and applies the torque logic to make the required shift. As an example, torque logic of an upshift process is shown in Figure 17.

Figure 18: Torque logic for the upshift

Active speed sensing technology provides the information of the rotational speed of the output shaft. Then, a PID controller controls the torque of the e-motor to increase or decrease the RPM of the input shaft based on the information from the speed sensor connected to the output shaft. The gearshift occurs when the RPM difference of the input and output shaft is not more than 30 RPM.

4.2 Actuator model

Actuator is a key element for the dog clutch engagement in 2-speed AMT gearbox.

Figure 19: Actuator model

The actuator model receives the information of the gear request and controls the position of the shift fork to make the shift. PID feedback controller is used to regulate the position of the actuator. The output position of the actuator is reflected by the position of the dog clutch in simulation. The Model of a DC motor and its control part as proposed in section 3.5 and shown in Figure 15 is simulated by a simple and ideal force source in simulation. The ideal force source block provides the necessary force to pull or push the shift fork to push the dog clutch in axial direction that ensures the gearshift.

5. Results

As it is mentioned earlier in section 4, the simulation platform consists of different models functioning parallelly. The main models are 1-D longitudinal vehicle model that outputs the acceleration demand of the vehicle based on the input data. The gear selection model that takes the acceleration demand as an input and calculates the torque demand for the required shift. The gearbox model that selects the suitable gear ratio to meet the desired torque requirements for the vehicle. Major Simulation results are discussed below.

5.1 E-motor torque

E-motor torque control is crucial in electric vehicles to vary the input shaft torque and rotational speed depending on the vehicle requirements. The gear ratio for the 1st and 2nd gear is 10:1 and 5:1 respectively. Negative torque is applied to brake the vehicle. The gear status and the e-motor torque response during the lower WLTC cycle is shown below.

Figure 20: Motor Torque

The torque response of the e-motor in Figure 20 shows that the motor torque is higher during the engagement on the 1st gear compared to the 2nd gear due to higher reduction ratio at 1st gear. The e-motor torque is very close to the ideal torque response, however there is a significant torque interruption during the gearshift that could be minimized by optimizing the shifting strategy and shifting control.

5.2 Speed of the shafts

Active speed sensing technology for the output shaft is implemented to synchronize the shaft speeds by controlling the motor torque. The gear status and the shaft speeds for the first 35 seconds of the lower WLTC cycle is shown below.

Figure 21: Input/output shafts speed

During the upshift, the e-motor is controlled to slow down to match the input shaft speed with the output shaft speed since the output shaft speed is lower at the current gear (1st gear) than the next gear (2nd gear). On the other hand, e-motor is controlled to speed up its spinning for the downshift as the speed of the current gear (2nd gear) is higher than the

targeted gear. The transmission system takes around 250 [ms] to perform the gearshift. This duration could be improved by optimizing the shifting control to lower the effect of torque interruption.

5.2 Driving cycle and vehicle speed

Since the targeted vehicle is a city delivery van, lower WLTC cycle is taken as a reference cycle to compare the vehicle performances.

Figure 22: Drive cycle and vehicle speed comparison

The trend of the vehicle speed is following the driving cycle and the error is within the limit that is explained in section 1.2. The parameters assumed for the simulations, such as the gearbox efficiency, inverter efficiency and different resistive force coefficients could be the reasons for the deviation. The speed profile of the vehicle could be improved by using the variable reducer and inverter efficiency instead of considering a constant efficiency.

6. Conclusion

Dog clutch along with the active speed sensing technology exhibits several desirable improvements over traditional synchronizers. These include shock reduction, backlash reduction, noise reduction, size reduction and an increase in shift speed. The removal of the friction synchronizer not only reduces the complexity of the system but can also save on material and manufacturing costs for those parts.

A rotational camshaft type actuator with a small DC shift motor was selected based on the analysis of the characteristics of 2-speed AMT gearbox due to its better shifting control possibility and reliability. A cascade controller was proposed to control the position of the actuator shift fork and the DC shift motor.

The threshold for the motor efficiency gain, torque, acceleration, minimum engagement duration, etc. were set up to avoid the continuous and unwanted gearshifts. Finally, 1-D longitudinal model, gearbox physical model, actuator control model were developed in matlab environment.

The simulation results show that the shifting solutions, shift control strategies are valid and reliable, which meets the gearbox and vehicle requirements. This set of shifting solutions and technologies thus has the potential for a significant global impact on 2-speed AMT gearbox.

7. Future Work

Areas of future investigation include the implementation of E-motor and DC shift motor model in simulation to simulate the behavior closer to the real vehicle and comparing the simulation results with the road vehicle data. Furthermore, reduction ratio optimization is very important to find the best compromise between the performance and energy consumption. Another area to investigate includes more research into the feasibility of incorporating the dog clutch design, actuator design into 2-speed AMT gearbox from both manufacturing and integration perspectives. A prototype design and implementation would certainly help to validate the scope of the proposed shifting solutions.

8. Acknowledgement

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to the Arrival's supervisors: Nicolangelo Piscitelli and Alexandre Charr for the continuous support, guidance, and encouragement throughout the project duration.

We would like to convey our appreciation to Ouafaé El Ganaoui-Mourlan, Powertrain Engineering Program director of IFP school for providing us a golden opportunity to work with an innovative and fast-growing company, Arrival. We would also like to thank Arrival and IFP school for trusting the project team and granting us an immense opportunity that encourages us to dedicate in electric and new mobility in professional future.

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10. Glossary

PWT: Powertrain

AMT: Automatic Manual Transmission

BEV: Battery Electric Vehicle

11. Annex

11.1 Tables

Table 1: Baseline Vehicle Specifications

Characteristics	Value	Unit	Label
Wheel radius	0.343	m	
Rolling resistance coefficient	0.0067	-	
Aerodynamic drag coefficient	0.348	-	
Vehicle frontal area	5.207	m ²	
Grip coefficient	0.8	-	
Axle loading factor	0.45	-	
Fully laden vehicle mass	4000	kg	
Unladen vehicle mass	2100	Kg	
Gravitational Acceleration	9.81	m/s ²	
Air density	1.225	kg/m ³	

Table 2: Gear Shifting Strategy

Execution order	Shifting type	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3	Condition 4	Condition 5	Condition 6
1	Downshift to $\nearrow \eta_{motor}$	η_{motor} gain > 1 %	η_{motor} down > η_{motor} Up	Torque enough	Last upshift occurred at least 5s before	Last downshift occurred at least 0.5s before	Acceleration > 0.15 m/s ²
2	Upshift to $\nearrow \eta_{motor}$	η_{motor} gain > 1	Torque enough	Last downshift occurred at least 5s before	Last upshift occurred at least 0.5s before	Acceleration > 0.15 m/s ²	
3	Downshift to \nearrow Torque	Torque not enough for current gear	Torque enough for targeted gear				
4	Upshift to \nearrow Torque	Torque not enough for current gear	Torque enough for targeted gear				

11.2 Figures

Figure 1: e-motor efficiency map

Figure 2: WLTC class 3 driving cycle

Figure 3: Project roadmap

Figure 4: 2-speed AMT without synchronizer

Figure 5: Dog-to-Dog vibro-impacts dynamics

Figure 6: Dog Clutch engagement

Figure 7: Sketch of the Torsional Compliance [1]

Figure 8: Exploded view of transmission system [1]

Figure 9: Double tooth length design [1]

Figure 10: 3D Model of a shift actuator [9]

Figure 11: Schematic diagram of shift actuator [9]

Figure 12: Camshaft rotation direction [9]

Figure 13: Expanded view of Groove in camshaft [9]

Figure 14: Equivalent electrical circuit

Figure 15: Actuator Controller

Figure 16: Main structure of the vehicle model

Figure 17: Gearbox model

Figure 18: Torque logic for the upshift

Figure 19: Actuator model

Figure 20: Motor Torque

Figure 21: Input/output shafts speed

Figure 22: Drive cycle and vehicle speed comparison